

EVALUATION OF THE REFRACTORY CHARACTERISTICS OF DUKKU CLAY DEPOSIT

A. M. Yami , M. A. B. Hassan and S. Umaru

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Federal University of Technology, P.M.B 2076, Yola, Adamawa State.
NIGERIA.

ABSTRACT

Dukku clay was investigated to determine its refractory characteristics. The result shows that it has a bulk modulus of 9.27g/cm^2 , porosity of 27.84%, linear shrinkage of 1.27% and cold crushing strength of 80.20kg/cm^3 . A thermal shock resistance of 25 cycles was obtained with specific gravity of 2.69g and refractoriness of 1300°C . The sample was also analyzed to determine its chemical composition by atomic absorption spectra photometry method (AAS969). The result of the chemical analysis shows that the alumina (Al_2O_3) content of the sample is 12.88% while the silica (SiO_2) content is 67.90%. The results obtained showed that Dukku clay can be used as refractory material for metals which melting points do not exceed 1300°C . Dukku clay can also be used for ceramics, pottery and building bricks production.

KEYWORDS; Ceramics, Clay Deposit, Firebricks, Refractory materials, Refractoriness.

INTRODUCTION

The demand for refractory materials for furnace building as well as other related high temperature processes is enormous. Hassan and Adewara (1993) reported that over 80 percent of the refractory materials are used by the metallurgical industries for the construction and upkeep of furnaces, reactor vessels, kilns and boilers. This is beside the fact that refractory materials are also used in non metallurgical industries such as cement, glass and hardware industries.

Refractory materials are generally considered as inorganic materials consisting of mixtures of oxides obtained from naturally occurring minerals and capable of withstanding very high temperature conditions without undue deformation, softening or change in composition. The most important aspect of a refractory is that it must be able to provide necessary thermal properties, support winding (electric resistance) and be capable of holding solid or liquid metals without entering into any undesirable chemical reaction with them. Thus refractory materials are characterized by the ability to withstand not only the heat but also chemical attack, abrasion, impact, and shock caused by thermal stresses.

Generally, refractory materials are classified according to their properties and characteristics. These classifications can be approached in a number of ways. A more detailed classification which demand consideration of the required end use and a guide to refractory compounds and the raw materials from which they are derived have been fully discussed by Coope (1986). Major classes of refractories are based on methods of manufacture, shape, national, and international standard, refractoriness and mineral composition.

Refractory products are required for various processes in chemical, ceramic, petrochemical, oil and iron and steel industries.

Nigeria is endowed with abundant mineral resources. These resources have not been sufficiently used. Nnuka and Adekwu (1998) reported that Nigeria spends over 2.27 billion Naira every year on the importation of refractories. The economic situation in the country has made it imperative for inward sourcing of raw materials. Some local clay deposits have been investigated with good results.

Studies on the Otukpo clay in Benue State by Nnuka and Agbo (2000) showed that the clay is Kaolinitic and belongs to the medium duty fire clay class of aluminium silicates. Agha (1998), reported that clays from Chanchanga, Bida, Suleja and Zungeru have better refractory and physical properties compared with imported ones

Table 1: Chemical Composition Analysis of Dukku Clay Deposit.

Constituents	Percentage
SiO ₂	67.90
Al ₂ O ₃	12.88
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.60
MgO	1.31
Na ₂ O	1.97
K ₂ O	0.06
LOI	6.60

Tests on clay deposits in Onibode, Ibamajo, Ijoko in Ogun State and Are in Ekiti State by Omowumi (2000), revealed that their properties compared favorably with imported refractories.

In view of reasons above and the fact that the Dukku clay deposit in Gombe State, is used only for local pottery and building bricks, investigation of its refractory properties is being conducted so as to reveal its other potentials for the refractory industry.

EXPERIMENTATION

All the experiments for this work were carried out at the National Metallurgical Development Centre, Jos, Plateau State.

The clay sample was dug from the deposit site by the use of a hoe. The sample was sun dried to reduce the moisture content and enhance grinding. 500g of the sun dried sample was ground to powder form a jaw crusher. 400g of the sample was taken for the physical property tests while the remainder was further ground to finer particles and then used for the chemical composition tests. The sample was weighed and dried in an oven at 110°C for one hour to ensure complete evaporation of the moisture.

The sample was then mixed with 8% water and stirred to form a homogeneous plastic paste. A cylindrical mould of steel plate, 50mm in height and 50mm diameter (American foundry mans society standard) was constructed. The plastic paste was then poured into the mould and rammed using a 3kg rammer. A suitable plunger was used to extrude the molded sample from the oil lubricated mould.

The prepared sample was dried in the oven at a temperature of 110°C to ensure evaporation of moisture. It was further fired in a muffle furnace at intervals of 100°C for every 10 minutes till the temperature of 1200°C was reached. The sample was then soaked at 1200°C for 8 hours and allowed to cool in the furnace for 24 hours.

EQUIPMENT USED

The equipment used in this investigation include, hoe, jaw crusher, ball mill, sand mixer, sand rammer, sieve shaker (type 4180), carbolite furnace, electric balance, cold crushing strength machine, disc die, hydraulic press and atomic absorption spectra photometry machine (model 969).

Chemical Composition Analysis

The ground sample was dried mixed with water and filtered. The analysis was performed on the atomic absorption spectrometry machine and the percentage composition of the various oxides recorded.

Table 2: Physical Properties of Dukku Clay Deposit.

Properties	Values
Bulk density (g/cm ³)	1.91
Apparent porosity (%)	27.15
Thermal shock resistance (cycles)	19
Linear shrinkage (%)	1.87
Specific gravity (g)	2.690
Cold crushing strength (kg/cm)	59.99
Refractoriness (°C)	1300

Cold Crushing Strength

This is the load at which cracks appear in the specimen. The test piece was prepared to standard size of 76.2mm cube on a flat surface. The test piece was fired in a furnace at 1100°C and the temperature maintained for 6 hours. It was cooled to room temperature and then placed on a compressive strength tester. Loads were applied axially by turning the hand wheel at a uniform rate until failure occurred. The load that caused cracks was then recorded.

Cold crushing strength (CCS) was calculated using the formula,

$$CCS = \frac{\text{Maximum Load (KN)}}{\text{Cross sectional Area (m}^2\text{)}} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Bulk Density

Bulk density is the weight per unit volume of a refractory material including the volume of open pore space.

A molded brick of the specimen measuring 60mm by 60mm by 15mm was prepared. The brick was air dried for 24 hours and then oven dried at 110°C, cooled in desiccator and weighed to the accuracy of 0.001 (dry weight), after which it was transferred to a beaker and heated for 30 minutes to assist in releasing trapped air. It was then cooled and the soaked weight (W) taken. The specimen was then suspended in water using a beaker placed on a weight balance and the suspended weight (S) measured.

The bulk density was then calculated using the relation,

$$\text{Bulk Density} = \frac{D\rho_w}{W - S} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where,

D=Dried weight.

W=Soaked weight.

S=Suspended weight.

ρ_w= Density of water.

Thermal Shock Resistance

The sample was placed in a muffle furnace preset at 1200°C for 10 minutes. It was then cooled outside the furnace for another 10 minutes and observed for cracks. This process was repeated until cracks were observed on the specimen.

Table: 3. Comparison of the Chemical Properties with International Standards.

Chemical Constituents	Dukku	*Fireclay	+Refractory bricks
SiO ₂ (%)	67.90	55-75	51-70
Al ₂ O ₃ (%)	12.88	25-45	25-40
Fe ₂ O ₃ (%)	2.6	0.5-2.0	0.5-2.4
MgO (%)	1.31	<2.0	
K ₂ O (%)	0.06	<2.0	
LOI (%)	6.6	12-15	

*Gilchrist (1977), +Grimshaw (1971)

The number of heating and cooling (cycles) before cracking occurred was recorded and this constitutes the thermal shock resistance.

Porosity

Porosity is the percentage relationship between the volume of the pore space and the total volume of a refractory.

A prepared clay sample was air dried for 24 hours. The piece was oven dried at 110°C for 24 hours. It was then fired to a temperature of 1100°C, cooled and transferred into a desiccator and weighed to the nearest 0.01g (Dried weight). The specimen was then transferred into a 250ml beaker in an empty vacuum desiccator. Water was then introduced into the beaker until the test piece was completely immersed. The specimen was allowed to soak in boiled water for 30 minutes being agitated from time to time to assist the release of trapped bubbles. The specimen was transferred into an empty vacuum desiccator to cool. The soaked weight (W) was recorded.

The specimen was then weighed when suspended in water using beaker placed on balance. This gave the suspended weight (S). The apparent porosity was calculated using,

$$ApparentPorosity = \frac{W - D}{W - S} \times 100\% \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where,
 W=Soaked weight
 D=Dried weight
 S=Suspended weight

Shrinkage

The test piece was made into a standard slab and a line marked along the length of slab. The distance between the two ends of the slab was measured with a vernier caliper. The sample was air dried for 24 hours and oven dried at 110°C for another 24 hours. It was then fired at 1100°C for 6 hours. The test piece was cooled to room temperature and measurement taken. The fired shrinkage was calculated from the relation,

$$FiredShrinkage = \frac{D_L - F_L}{D_L} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where,
 D_L=Initial fired length.
 F_L=Final fired length.

Table 4: Comparison of the Determined Properties of Dukku Clay with Some Established Refractory Standards.

Constituents	Dukku Values	*Fireclay
Bulk density g/cm ²	1.91	1.71- 2.1
Apparent porosity %	27.15	20-30
Thermal shock resistance cycles	19	25-30**
Linear shrinkage %	1.87	7-10
Specific gravity g	2.690	
Cold crushing strength kg/cm	59.99	15,000**
Refractoriness °C	1300	1500-1700

*Gilchrist (1977), **Omowumi (2000)

Specific Gravity

The specific gravity test is usually conducted on materials that do not dissolve in or get attacked by water. The test piece is cut from within the core of a refractory shape and crushed to a size not exceeding 3mm. The crushed material is then mixed and reduced to a 50g sample by cooling and quartering. The material obtained in the above state of fineness is dried at 105 – 110°C to a constant weight and placed in a glass stoppered weighing bottle to weigh 8 – 12g sample. A pycnometer with stopper was dried at 105 – 110°C, cooled in a desiccators and its weight (W) noted. The pycnometer was filled with distilled water at room temperature. The stopper was put in place. Its outer surface is dried that has overflowed through the stopper and its weight (W1) noted. The pycnometer was emptied of water and dried. The test sample was put in it from the weighing bottle and its weight (W) noted, with the stopper in position. The pycnometer was filled with distilled water to about half its capacity and boiled gently for 10 to 15 minutes to avoid loss of sample due to popping. The pycnometer was then filled with distilled water and cooled to room temperature in a water bath. The stopper was put in position and excess water overflowing the pycnometer through its stopper was wiped off. The outer surface of the pycnometer was dried with a towel. The weight (W2) of the pycnometer containing the test sample and water was recorded. The specific gravity was then calculated from the relation below,

$$Specific\ Gravity = \frac{W - W_p}{(W - W_p) - (W_2 - W_1)} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

Refractoriness

This is the measure of the fusibility of a material and indicates the temperature at which the material softens.

The parametric cone equivalence (PCE) method was used to determine the refractoriness of the Dukku clay. The clay sample was dried and ground to pass a 30 mesh British standard (B.S 1610R1942) test sieve and 50g was further ground to pass a 72 mesh sieve. Sieving was frequent to avoid excess of very fine powder. The sample was then thoroughly mixed, made into a plastic mass with water and an organic binder (0.5% maximum ash content) was added. The test piece was then formed in a suitable mould. Calcinations of the clay were conducted at 1000°C. The mould was shaped into a pyramid with a triangular base. One edge of the pyramid was perpendicular to the base and 3.81cm long each side of the triangular base is 1.27cm. A tolerance of 0.16cm was allowed in the dimensions of the base.

The test piece was mounted at the center of a refractory plaque and fixed with cement consisting calcined alumina. The edge of the test piece was vertical to the base. British standard pyrometric cones were cemented to the plaque but oriented so that they would bend away from the test piece the numbers facing inwards. The edges opposite the

numbers were vertical. The test piece with the surrounding pyrometric cones was placed in the furnace, the temperature raised at the rate of 10 to 15°C per minute to an estimated temperature of 200° below the equating temperature. The rate of temperature rise was observed by the use of an optical pyrometer. The test continued till the tip of the test cone had bent over level with the base. The plaque bearing the specimen was removed from the furnace and the test piece examined when cold.

The refractoriness is the number of the pyrometric cones that has bent over to a large extent similar to the test cone. The temperature is then read off from the equivalent of the cone number.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of our investigations are tabulated in Table 1 and Table 2.

Chemical Composition: The result of the chemical composition analysis shows that the alumina (Al_2O_3) content of the sample is 12.88%, which is below the 25-45% required for fireclay and 25-40% for refractory bricks as shown in Table 3. The alumina content in clay is a strong indicator of its refractoriness. The higher the amount of alumina in clay, the higher is the refractoriness of the clay. The silica (SiO_2) content as shown in Table 3 is 67.90%, which satisfies both the ranges for fireclay and refractory bricks. This means it can be used for lining of heat treatment furnaces, melting furnaces for low melting point metals, liquid metal ladles and portions of blast furnaces. The iron oxide (Fe_2O_3) content of 2.6% is slightly higher than the standard of 0.5-2.4 for refractory bricks. Such level of iron oxide usually imparts a reddish color to clay when fired, so making it attractive as a ceramic raw material according to Nnuka and Agbo (2000). This high iron oxide content also affects the high temperature characteristics of the clay, such as the fired strength. This makes the clay in this category attractive and suitable for structural Engineering works.

Physical Properties.

Apparent Porosity: The value obtained is 27.15%, which is within the range of 20-30% required for firebrick clay as reported by Chester (1973).

Bulk Density: The average bulk density of Dukku clay is 1.91. From the comparison with the Gilchrist (1977) range, it can be seen that Dukku clay satisfies the condition for firebricks (Table 4).

Cold Crushing Strength: The minimum requirement for refractory brick is 15000 kg/cm^2 while the value obtained for Dukku clay is 59.99 kg/cm^2 (Table 4). Cold crushing strength shows the effect of firing on ceramic bound and this may be affected by firing, sintering characteristics and pressing methods.

Thermal Shock Resistance: As can be seen from Table 4, the thermal shock resistance of the sample is short of the acceptable range of 25-30 cycles. The practical implication of this is that its use restricted to lining of ladles and slag pots which are early mended at shock intervals.

Linear Shrinkage: The linear shrinkage of Dukku clay as obtained from the experiment is 1.87%, which is lower than the internationally accepted values of 7-10%. Refractory clays which have the greater amount of stability are supposed to be the best.

Refractoriness: The temperature obtained is 1300°C. This is an indication of poor refractoriness. Fireclay refractory bricks should have refractoriness in the range of 1500-1700°C (Table 3). This low value of refractoriness is as a result of the high silica content of the clay. The implication of this is that its use is restricted to the processing of materials which melting points do not exceed 1300°C.

Loss on Ignition: The value obtained is lower than the range recommended for fireclays which have values in the range of 12-15% (Table 4). Loss on ignition values are often required to be low (Omowumi 2000). This is because of its effect on the porosity of refractory bricks. The low value is an indication of low porosity value of the brick.

CONCLUSION

Dukku clay has been investigated and its suitability as an industrial raw material has been discussed in view of its chemical and physical properties. It is found to be a good substitute for imported refractory materials used in our metallurgical industries for processing refractory bricks needed for lining the walls of furnaces, soaking pits, ovens, ladles, crucibles and kilns. Proper blending with other clays or additives, such as sawdust and rice husk will bring the era of importing refractory bricks to an end.

Further work need to be carried out to determine other important properties like refractoriness-under-load and slag resistance. The clay should be exploited not only for making burnt bricks but also for agricultural, chemical and paper industries.

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Corresponding Author:

S. Umaru, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Federal University of Technology, P.M.B 2076, Yola, Adamawa State. NIGERIA. bnumar@gmail.com